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FACTORS AFFECTING BALANCED SCORECARD AMONG THE I.T. INDUSTRY EXECUTIVES IN INDIA

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Abstract

Balanced Scorecard elaborates the mission and strategy of the organization by providing clarity to guide the employees in order to make them more informative for discharging their respective functions efficiently. It is also a tool which is used to make Performance Management System more effective for improvement of the performance of employees.

In this study we investigate the factors which are likely to affect the Balanced Scorecard among the I.T. Industry executives in India as I.T. Industry has transformed India's image from a slow moving bureaucratic economy to a land of innovative entrepreneurs in spite of all odds.

The present study is a survey research to collect the data because it is found to be the most suitable method for answering the research questions and for this a structured questionnaire has been used. Convenience Sampling is used to collect the data from executives of I.T. Industry of National Capital Region who are thought to have desired information. Questionnaire of this research aims at collecting quantifiable data for the analysis. This requires the adoption of Likert Scale to measure the employee attitude. Each degree of agreement is given a numerical score and the respondents' total score is computed by summing these scores.

Factor Analysis of Balanced Scorecard makes the construct of different sub-factors in order of their importance for Performance Management System in I.T. Industry. The results are obtained through orthogonal rotation with Varimax (least significant factors) in which it is found that customer perspective, financial perspective and learning & growth perspective are highly significant while internal process perspective is moderately significant.

This study has given a basis of data to the management through which management can take a decision to implement Performance Management System in a better way. Such study may be replicated in different business sectors within India.

Key Words: Balanced Scorecard, I.T. Industry, Performance Management System, Executives.

Introduction:

Balance – a seven letter word provides the essence of a healthy organization. Balance is necessary for efficient and effective movement. Similarly, for effective Performance Management System, Balanced Scorecard works as “Balance” that means balance from all perspectives – Customer, Learning & Growth, Financial and Internal Process.

Since the Balanced Scorecard was invented in 1990s, it was received a wide range of use and promotion in the global business community, and some of the major international business houses have successfully used the Balanced Scorecard, which makes it possible to increase their performance greatly.

Balanced Scorecard was presented by Harvard Business School professor Robert S. Kaplan and the rejuvenation of the Global Strategy Group's founder and president, David P. Norton. Balanced Scorecard showed the great vitality since it appeared. It can effectively help enterprises give solution on two major problems - performance evaluation and the implementation of the strategy. In 1,000 companies in the world which "Fortune" magazine published, 70% of which used the Balanced Scorecard system; "Harvard Business Review" sees it as the most influential strategic management tool in 75 years.

Balanced Scorecard is not only an indicator of appraisal system, but also a strategic management system. The use of the Balanced Scorecard breaks the traditional single-use financial indicators methods which measure performance. It adds the future drivers in the financial indicators, which is customer factors, internal processes and learning & growth.

- Customer: The managers confirm the competition's customers and market segments which the organization will take part in, and turn the goal into a set of indicators. Such as

market share, customer retention rate, the rate of customers, customer satisfaction, customer profitability level.

- Internal process: In order to attract and retain the target customers and meet the requirements of shareholders about financial returns, managers need to focus on customer satisfaction and those internal processes, and establish measurable indicators. In this regard, BSC is not only paying attention to a simple process to improve the existing operators, but to confirm the request of customers and shareholders as a starting point, and to satisfy customers and shareholders.
- Learning and growth: It confirms an investment which the organization must be carried out in order to achieve long-term performance in the future, including the ability of employees, organization information system and so on.
- Financial: The financial success in organizations must be translated into the ultimate success. Only to translate the improvements of product quality, time to complete orders, productivity, new product development and customer satisfaction into increased sales, reduction of operating cost and improvement in asset turnover can bring benefits for the organization.

Below Table shows the Scorecard of Manager – HR which includes all the four perspectives of Balanced Scorecard (customer perspective, financial perspective, internal process perspective and learning and growth perspective). Accordingly, their respective Key Result Area (KRA) and Key Performance Indicator (KPI) are identified. Thereafter each KRA has specific weightage which is assigned according to their importance.

Table-1 (Scorecard for Manager – HR)

Scorecard for Manager – HR									
Perspective	Strategic Objectives (KRA)	Performance Measure (KPI)	Weightage	Calibration					Achievement
				1	2	3	4	5	
Financial	Budget	Timely analysis of budget to monitor its adherence	10%						
Process	Annual increment	Compilation of increment data for payroll purpose	10%						
	Trackers	Create Dash Board: Personnel, Recruitment and maintain trackers	10%						
	Job Design	Standardization of Job Design	10%						
	SOPs	100% compliance of SOPs	10%						
Customer	Recruitment	Searching of cv on web portal as per recruitment plan	10%						
		To complete recruitment as agreed by HOD	20%						
People	Employee development	Develop employee for recruitment of asst. managers	20%						

Objective:

The objective of this study is to find out the degree of relationship between Balanced Scorecard and its sub-factors (customer perspective, internal process perspective, financial perspective and learning and growth perspective) and also with Performance Management System.

Literature Review:

Strategy and vision are situated at the core of Balanced Scorecard. The necessary action or behavior must be taken by the employees in order to achieve the agreed goals.

Figure-1 (Balanced Scorecard Model)

Source: Adapted from Kaplan and Norton [9]

Kaplan and Norton [9] have highlighted four important processes in linking BSC with the strategy as follows:

- a. Overcoming the vision barriers through translation of strategy: The usage of BSC in this research is to provide guidance to the organization on the overall strategy that has translated nebulous declarations into measurable achievement. The mission, vision and core values of the organization would only be established if the organization took a necessary action or behave accordingly and thus, BSC acts as a tool to transform vision based on the management’s strategy.
- b. Cascading the scorecard to overcome the people`s barriers: BSC elaborates on the mission and the strategy by providing “line of sight” from the director’s office to the front line (Azhar, R [2]). Thus, employees would be able to know specific functions and contributions to the overall outcome of the organizations. Hence, the employees could

agree to emphasize on the performance drivers that could lead to the desired outcomes by the management.

- c. Strategic resource allocation to overcome the resource barriers: The resources and processes are the two critical elements that BSC could assist in ensuring the success of managing the organization (Kaplan & Norton [10]). The missed opportunity on recruitment and the inability of the firm to realize the processes would affect the final outcome.
- d. Strategic Learning to overcome barriers: This research will identify the processes carried out in the course of implementing the performance management system by I.T. Industry. The lack of information had caused the obtained knowledge to be short term in nature and obsolete. Hence, it is critical to gain the accurate information combined by the vision, resources and people`s barriers in the organization.

The ability of BSC to translate strategy into everyday activities of the employees and management has been proven through translated work by breaking down the components of strategy statement (Kaplan & Norton [10]). The vague and explicit direction of top management would be transformed into a clear and concise objective. Hence, it clarifies the role of every employee in a top-down movement. These activities are also known as creating a strategy map. Thus, by creating a strategy map, the employees, customers and the stakeholders would be able to know and understand the goal or the aim of the organization. Hence, as the organization cascades the strategy map from the higher level management to the lower divisions and sections, employees will gain a better insight on what their specific roles and contribution in achieving the unified organization goals. Therefore, this research will attempt to substantiate the existence of causal relationship between BSCs components that are being used in I.T. Industry.

The Balanced Scorecard approach to management (Kaplan & Norton [9]) has gained prominence in performance in accounting management research this decade. Kaplan and Norton [8] have made a revolution which has set the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) as a comprehensive set of measures which could benefit an organization in increasing the level of service quality and production. Thus, basically, the financial perspective must be complemented by other BSC perspectives such as internal processes and learning and growth in order to increase the level of efficiency and productivity of an organization. However, according to Kaplan and Norton [9],

‘the financial perspective is not the bottom-line objective for I.T. Industry but customer perspective is’. Hence, it has been found to be critical for the PMS using the BSC to translate all the relationships which could lead to customer satisfaction as the main focus especially in case of I.T. Industry.

According to Simons [13], Performance Management System is defined as the formal and information-based procedure managers used to maintain in order to achieve the target. De Walle [5] has proposed PMS definition as the financial and non-financial information for the management that has led to the managerial action for decision making. Performance Management System has been defined as ‘an integrated set of planning and review procedures which cascade down through the organization to provide a link between each individual and the overall strategy of the organization’ (Smith & Goddard [14]). Thus, this definition has been adopted in this research. Dessler [6] has defined Performance Management System as ‘the process that unites goal setting, performance appraisal and development into a single common system’ whose aim is to ensure that the strategic aim of the firm be fully supported by the employees’ performance. Glendinning [7] has proposed the definition of Performance Management System as ‘the distinguishing feature that explicitly measures the employees’ training, standard setting, appraisal and feedback relative to how his or her performance should be and their contribution to achieving the company’s goal’.

Nevertheless, Kaplan and Norton [10], state that almost ninety-five percent of the typical workforces have not comprehended the mission and strategy of the firm. The BSC could provide the four critical perspectives that could lead to the critical decision-making by the management of the firm. However, Atkinson et al. [1] note that the balanced scorecard deserves intensive research attention and it could be considered as the most significant development in accounting management. It is noted that the main intention and priority of I.T. Industry is to serve the employees. The focal point of the perspective would be the management’s strategy and meeting the people’s demand. Hence, some authorities including Bourne and Bourne [3], Paladino [11] as well as Parmenter [12] have stated that it has been difficult for managers to develop a set of key performance indicators which could be related to both business performance and meeting social goals. Thus, the design and structure of the PMS in I.T. Industry should be studied.

Methodology:

Primary data means original data that are collected specially for the purpose in mind. It means, an investigator collects the data from the target population by using close-ended questionnaire. Primary data is important for all areas of research because it is unvarnished information about the results of an experiment or observation. It is like the eyewitness testimony at a trial. Primary data is the specific information collected by the person who is doing the research.

The nature of this study is descriptive as perception, attitude and characteristics of the different group participating in the survey could be determined by descriptive research as suggested (Cavana, Delahaye & Sekaran [4]). Descriptive research is undertaken to describe the situation, community, phenomena, outcome or programme. A total of 505 questionnaires were distributed among the executives of five branches of different I.T. Industry of National Capital Region in the month of October, 2015. Out of the sample size 505, a total of 410 questionnaires were received (i.e. Response Rate at 81.18%) and found correct and retained for further analysis. In this study Convenience Sampling is used to collect the data that would not have been possible using probability sampling techniques. Data has been collected from the respondents who are the executives in I.T. Company of National Capital Region. It was very difficult to get the access from them because of their busy schedule in the Company. Management of I.T. Company was unable to give permission to conduct the research and get a list of all employees in the organization. However, taking the seriousness and potential of this study, Management has granted permission for one day to conduct the research and collect as many survey responses as possible.

Convenience Sampling is a simple process to collect the data and move on to other aspects of the study. Setting up for this type of sampling can be done by simply creating a questionnaire and distributing it to the targeted group. Through this method we have easily finished collecting the data in a matter of hours, free from worry about whether it is an accurate representation. This allows for a great ease of research, letting us focus on analyzing the data rather than interviewing and carefully selecting each participant.

Measurement implies the process of information which can be subject to analysis. In attitude measurement, the researcher is primarily interested in measuring the state of mind of the respondents. It may include factors such as awareness, attitudes and decision processes.

Questionnaire of this research was aimed at collecting quantifiable data for the analysis. This required the adoption of an appropriate rating scale to measure the employee attitude and morale. Some of the rating scales were tried and found not suitable for the proposed work except Likert Scale.

Analysis & Interpretation:

Customer perspective: Recent management philosophy has shown an increasing realization of the importance of customer focus and customer satisfaction in any business. These are leading indicators: if customers are not satisfied, they will eventually find other suppliers that will meet their needs. Poor performance from this perspective is thus a leading indicator of future decline, even though the current financial picture may look good. In developing metrics for satisfaction, customers should be analyzed in terms of kinds of customers and the kinds of processes for which we are providing a product or service to those customer groups.

Management understanding about the specific needs of the customers: The following Table shows the extent to which management understand the specific needs of the customers.

Table-2 (Management Understanding about the Needs of the Customers)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	18	4.39	4.39
2	Disagree	84	20.48	24.87
3	Neutral	98	23.90	48.77
4	Agree	160	39.02	87.79
5	Strongly Agree	50	12.21	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

It is observed from the Table that 39.02 per cent respondents agreed that management of I.T. Industry understand the specific needs of the customers, followed by 12.21 per cent respondents

who strongly agreed and opined that management understand the needs of the customers. On the other way only 4.39 per cent respondents strongly disagreed with the management understanding about the needs of the customers, followed by 20.48 per cent respondents having the similar opinion. However a significant portion of the total respondents (i.e. 23.90%) are neutral towards the management understanding about the specific needs of the customers.

Customer's satisfaction with the organization (I.T. Industry) policy: The following Table depicts the satisfaction of customers with the organization (I.T. Industry) policy.

Table-3 (Customer's Satisfaction with the Organization Policy)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	15	3.65	3.65
2	Disagree	41	10	13.65
3	Neutral	125	30.48	44.13
4	Agree	157	38.29	82.42
5	Strongly Agree	72	17.58	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Table reveals that majority of the sample respondents i.e. 38.29 percent are of the opinion that customers are satisfied with the organization's policy, followed by 17.58 per cent respondents who have also the similar notion about the customer's satisfaction with the organization's policy. However a major portion of the total respondents i.e. 30.48 per cent are totally neutral towards the organization's policy. On the other hand a small portion i.e. 4.39 per cent respondents are strongly disagree, and not satisfied with the organization policy of I.T. Industry, followed by 10 per cent respondents who have also the similar opinion regarding the customer's satisfaction with the organization policy.

PMS influence the employee's behavior that boosts confidence among the customers: The following Table shows that PMS influence the employee's behavior that boosts confidence among the customers of I.T. Industry.

Table-4 (PMS Influence the Employee’s Behavior that Boost Confidence among the Customers)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	23	5.60	5.60
2	Disagree	91	22.19	27.79
3	Neutral	78	19.02	46.81
4	Agree	154	37.56	84.37
5	Strongly Agree	64	15.63	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Figure-2 (PMS Influence Employee’s Behavior)

From the aforesaid Table it is observed that a significant portion of the total respondents i.e. 37.56 per cent opined that PMS influence the employee’s behavior that boost the confidence among the customers of I.T. Industry, followed by 15.63 per cent respondents who also agree

and have the similar opinion. On the other extreme only 5.60 per cent respondents strongly disagree that PMS influence the employee's behavior that boost the confidence among the customers of I.T. Industry, followed by 22.19 per cent respondents who simply disagree with the notion as given above. However 19.02 per cent respondents do not express any opinion in relation to the role of PMS in influencing the behavior of employees that boost the confidence among the customers of I.T. Industry.

Learning & growth perspective: This perspective includes employee training and corporate cultural attitudes related to both individual and corporate self-improvement. In a knowledge-worker organization, people -- the only repository of knowledge -- are the main resource. In the current climate of rapid technological change, it is becoming necessary for knowledge workers to be in a continuous learning mode. Metrics can be put into place to guide managers in focusing training funds where they can help the most. In any case, learning and growth constitute the essential foundation for success of any knowledge-worker organization.

PMS improves the effectiveness of training programmes: the following Table shows the extent to which PMS improves the effectiveness of training programmes of the I.T. Industry.

Table-5 (PMS Improves the Effectiveness of Training Programme)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	27	6.58	6.58
2	Disagree	53	12.92	19.50
3	Neutral	80	19.51	39.01
4	Agree	160	39.02	78.03
5	Strongly Agree	90	21.97	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

From the above Table it is discerned that majority of sample respondents i.e. 39.02 per cents agreed that PMS improves the effectiveness of training programmes of I.T. Industry, followed by 21.97 per cent respondents who are strongly agreed that PMS plays an important role in

improving the effectiveness of training programmes. Whereas only 6.58 per cent sample respondents strongly disagree and reject the notion that PMS improve the effectiveness of training programmes, followed by 12.92 per cent sample respondents having the similar opinion. However, 19.51 per cent of sample respondents are indifferent towards the role of PMS in improving the effectiveness of training programmes of I.T. Industry.

PMS helping the staff to monitor progress towards intended programmes: The following Table shows the role of PMS in helping the staff to monitor progress towards intended programmes of I.T. Industry.

Table-6 (PMS Helps the Staff to Monitor Progress Towards Intended Programmes)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	20	4.87	4.87
2	Disagree	96	23.41	28.28
3	Neutral	89	21.70	49.98
4	Agree	93	22.68	72.66
5	Strongly Agree	112	27.34	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Table shows the opinion of the sample respondents regarding the role of PMS in helping the staff to monitor progress towards intended programmes of I.T. Industry. It is observed from the Table that majority of sample respondents i.e. 27.34 per cent are strongly agreed that PMS helping the staff of I.T. Industry to monitor progress towards intended programmes, followed by 22.68 per cent respondents who are also having the similar opinion regarding the role of PMS in helping the staff to monitor progress towards intended programmes of I.T. Industry. On the other extreme only 4.87 per cent of sample respondents strongly disagreed reject the role of PMS in monitoring the organizational progress towards the intended programmes, followed by 23.41 per

cent sample respondents who are also demise the PMS in monitoring the organizational progress. Whereas 21.70 per cent sample respondents do not express any views and remains neutral regarding the role of PMS in monitoring the organizational progress.

PMS for staff participation in programme development: The following Table talks about the PMS for staff participation in programme development in I.T. Industry.

Table-7 (PMS for Staff Participation in Programme Development)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	28	6.82	6.82
2	Disagree	21	5.12	11.94
3	Neutral	143	34.87	46.81
4	Agree	145	35.36	82.17
5	Strongly Agree	73	17.83	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Table discerns that a significant portion of the total respondents i.e. 35.36 per cent are agreed that PMS increases the staff participation in the process of programme development, followed by 17.83 per cent respondents were strongly agreed and having the similar opinion regarding the PMS and its role in the process of programme development. On the other side 6.82 sample respondents strongly disagree and demise the role of PMS that influence the staff participation in the process of programme development, followed by 5.12 per cent respondents having the similar opinion. However, 34.87 per cent of sample respondents are neutral towards the PMS for influencing the staff participation in the process of programme development.

Financial perspective: Timely and accurate funding data will always be a priority, and managers will do whatever necessary to provide it. In fact, often there is more than enough handling and processing of financial data. With the implementation of a corporate database, it is hoped that more of the processing can be centralized and automated. But the point is that the current

emphasis on financials leads to the “unbalanced” situation with regard to other perspectives. There is perhaps a need to include additional financial-related data, such as risk assessment and cost-benefit data, in this category.

PMS improve cost saving programmes of the I.T. Industry: The following Table shows the extent to which PMS improve cost saving programmes of the I.T. Industry.

Table-8 (PMS Improve Cost Saving Programmes of I.T. Industry)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	26	6.34	6.34
2	Disagree	97	23.65	29.99
3	Neutral	103	25.12	55.11
4	Agree	150	36.58	91.69
5	Strongly Agree	34	8.31	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Table depicts the role of performance management system in cost saving programmes of I.T. Industry. A significant portion of the total respondents i.e. 36.58 per cent are agreed and opined that performance management system improve cost saving programmes of I.T. Industry, followed by 8.31 per cent sample respondents who are strongly agreed and having the similar opinion as given above. On the other hand only 6.34 and 23.65 per cent respondents show the contradictory opinion regarding the role of performance management system in cost saving programmes of I.T. Industry. However, 25.12 per cent sample respondents are neutral and do not express any views regarding the role of PMS in cost saving programmes of I.T. Industry.

PMS create a link between performance measures and budget decisions in the I.T. Industry.

Table-9 (PMS create a link b/w Performance Measures & Budget Decisions)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	22	5.36	5.36
2	Disagree	56	13.65	19.01
3	Neutral	90	21.95	40.96
4	Agree	146	35.60	76.56
5	Strongly Agree	96	23.44	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

From the aforesaid Table it is depicted that majority of sample respondents i.e. 35.60 per cent agreed that PMS create a useful link between performance measures and budget decisions of I.T. Industry, followed by 23.44 per cent respondents who are strongly agreed with the notion as given above and have the similar opinion. On the other side only 5.36 per cent respondents strongly disagree and reject the role of PMS in creating a link between performance measures and budget decisions, followed by 13.65 per cent respondents who desist the role of PMS in creating the link between performance measures and budget decisions. However, 21.95 percent sample respondents are neutral and do not express any views regarding the statement as given above.

Internal Process Perspective: This perspective refers to internal business processes. Metrics based on this perspective allow the managers to know how well their business is running, and whether its products and services conform to customer requirements (the mission). These metrics have to be carefully designed by those who know these processes most intimately; with our unique missions these are not something that can be developed by outside consultants.

PMS improve relationship between superiors and subordinates: The following Table shows the role of PMS in improving the relationship between superiors and subordinates in I.T. Industry.

Table-10 (PMS Improve Relationship between Superiors and Subordinates)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	23	5.60	5.60
2	Disagree	95	23.17	28.77
3	Neutral	110	26.82	55.59
4	Agree	145	35.36	90.95
5	Strongly Agree	37	9.05	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

The above Table talks about the superior and subordinate relationship in I.T. Industry. It is observed that majority of sample respondents i.e. 35.36 per cent agree that PMS improve the relationship between superiors and subordinates in the I.T. Industry, followed by 9.05 per cent respondents who strongly agree with the statement as given above. On the other hand, 5.60 per cent respondents strongly disagree and demise the role of PMS in improving the relationship between superiors and subordinates, followed by 23.17 per cent respondents having the similar opinion. However, 26.82 per cent sample respondents are indifferent towards the role of PMS in improving the relationship between superiors and subordinates in I.T. Industry. PMS help to reduce duplication of services: The following Table shows the role of PMS in reducing the duplication of services in the I.T. Industry.

Table-11 (PMS Help to Reduce Duplication of Services)

S. No.	Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
1	Strongly Disagree	28	6.82	6.82
2	Disagree	60	14.63	21.45
3	Neutral	90	21.95	43.40
4	Agree	140	34.14	77.54
5	Strongly Agree	92	22.46	100
	Total	410	100	

Source: Compiled from primary data

Figure-3 (PMS Help to Reduce Duplication of Services)

The aforesaid Table depicts the role of PMS in reducing the duplication of services. From the above Table it is observed that majority of sample respondents i.e. 34.14 opined that PMS helps to reduce the duplication of services, followed by 22.46 per cent sample respondents who strongly agree that PMS helps in reducing the duplication of services. On the other extreme only 6.82 per cent sample respondents strongly disagree in respect of any role of PMS in reducing the duplication of services, followed by 14.63 per cent sample respondents also disagree and demise the role of PMS in reducing the duplication of services. However, 21.95 per cent sample respondents are neutral and do not express any views regarding the role of PMS in reducing the duplication of services in the I.T. Industry.

Findings:

- a. As per Table-2, 39% respondents agree that the management understands the specific needs of the customers while 12% strongly agree with this. The opinion of 24% respondents is neutral while another 20% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 51% respondents agree that the management understands the specific needs of the customers.
- b. According to Table-3, 38% respondents agree that customers are satisfied with the organization’s policy while 18% strongly agree with this. The opinion of 30%

respondents is neutral while 10% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 56% respondents agree that customers are satisfied with the organization's policy.

- c. As per Table-4, 38% respondents agree that Performance Management System influence the behavior of employees that instill the confidence in customers while 16% strongly agree with this. The opinion of 19% respondents is neutral while 22% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 54% respondents agree that Performance Management System influence the behavior of employees that instill the confidence in customers.
- d. According to Table-5, 39% respondents agree that Performance Management System improves the effectiveness of training program while 22% strongly agree with this. The opinion of another 20% respondents is neutral while 13% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 61% respondents agree that Performance Management System improves the effectiveness of training program.
- e. As per Table-6, 23% respondents agree that Performance Management System helps staff to monitor progress towards intended programs while 27% strongly agree with this. The opinion of 22% respondents is neutral while another 23% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 50% respondents agree that Performance Management System helps staff to monitor progress towards intended programs.
- f. According to Table-7, 35% respondents agree that Performance Management System increases staff participation in the process of developing program while 18% strongly agree with this. The opinion of another 35% respondents is neutral while 5% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 53% respondents agree that Performance Management System increases the staff participation in the process of developing program.
- g. As per Table-8, 37% respondents agree that Performance Management System helps to improve cost saving program of the I.T. Industry while 20% strongly agree with this. The opinion of 25% respondents is neutral while 12% respondents disagree with this. It means 57% respondents agree that Performance Management System helps to improve cost saving program of the I.T. Industry.
- h. According to Table-9, 36% respondents agree that Performance Management System creates a link between performance measures and budget decisions while 23% strongly

agree with this. The opinion of another 22% respondents is neutral while 14% disagree with this notion. It means 59% respondents agree that Performance Management System creates a link between performance measures and budget decisions.

- i. As per Table-10, 35% respondents agree that Performance Management System improves the relationship between superior and subordinate while 15% strongly agree with this. The opinion of 27% respondents is neutral while 17% disagree with this notion. It means 50% respondents agree that Performance Management System improves the relationship between superior and subordinate.
- j. According to Table-11, 34% respondents agree that Performance Management System helps to reduce duplication of services in the I.T. Industry while 22% strongly agree with this. The opinion of another 22% respondents is neutral while 15% respondents disagree with this notion. It means 56% respondents agree that Performance Management System helps to reduce duplication of services in the I.T. Industry.

Limitations:

The Information Technology Act 2005 which is applicable and operated in India under the Law is peculiar in nature. Thus, the findings of this research may not be generalized or applied to other countries.

Social prejudice, bias and discriminating behavior have been found to be unavoidable in any social science research. This has been seen once again as one of the limitations.

Scope for future work:

This study may be replicated in different business sectors within India other than the I.T. Industry. The study may be conducted in different environmental contexts and settings which can provide additional insights about the subject area.

Conclusions:

This study clearly indicates that there is evidence of a positive significant relationship between Balanced Scorecard and its sub-factors (customer perspective, internal process perspective, financial perspective and learning and growth perspective) and also with Performance Management System in I.T. Industry. The purpose of this study is to better understand

Performance Management System, difficulties executives very frequently experience and the contribution of Performance Management System for the development of I.T. Industry in India. It is no doubt that I.T. Sector has changed the mindset of youngsters in India for making themselves more innovative as this sector has the largest paying capacity to the fresher. Their success is because of effective implementation of Performance Management System. They train the fresher, motivate them for achieving the target on scheduled time, they share the ideas; they maintain transparency and so on. But in some cases, executives in I.T. Industry experience difficulties because of compulsion they feel. For this, executives should be involved in the decision-making process. Management should implement ESOP (Employees Stock Option Plan) by issuing shares to the executives. In this way, executives will get ownership right and will be more loyal towards the organization. This study shows that all considered factors are dependent on employees of the organization. If any organization wants to improve these factors it has to help, support and take care of its staff and hence it will benefit staff of the organization and in turn it will help the organization.

References

1. Atkinson, AA, Balakrishnan, R, Booth, P, Cote, JM, Grout, T, Mali, T, Roberts, H, Ulan E & Wu, A 1997, 'New direction in management accounting research', Journal of Management Accounting Research 9: 80-108.
2. Azhar, R 2009, 'Adoption of performance measurement among Malaysian Public Sector', Master Thesis, University of Malaya, Malaysia.
3. Bourne, MCS & Bourne, PA 2007, Balanced Scorecard – Instant Manager, Hodder, London
4. Cavana, RY, Delahaye, BL & Sekaran, U 2001, Applied Business Research: Qualitative and Quantitative Methods, Singapore: John Wiley & Sons.
5. De Walle, SV 2007, 'International Comparisons of Public Sector Performance: How to move ahead?' Presented at IRSKPIXI, Potsdam, 2-4 April 2007.
6. Dessler, G 2008, Human Resource Management. 11th Edition, Pearson Education Inc., Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
7. Glendinning, P 2002, 'Performance Management: Pariah or Messiah', Public Personnel Management 31, no. 2 (Summer 2002), pp. 161-178.
8. Kaplan, R & Norton DP 1992, 'The Balance Scorecard- Measures that drive performance'. Harvard Business Review, January-February: 71-79.
9. Kaplan, R & Norton DP 1996, The Balance Scorecard: Translating Strategy into Action. Harvard Business School Press, Boston, M.A.

10. Kaplan, R & Norton DP 2001, 'The strategy-focused organisation', Ivey Business Journal, May/June.
11. Paladino, B 2008, Five Key Principles of Corporate Performance Management, John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
12. Parmenter, D 2007, Chapter 1-Introduction. Performance management: Developing, Implementing and Using Winning KPIs, John Wiley & Sons.
13. Simons, R 1991, 'Strategic orientation and top management attention to control systems', Strategic Management Journal, 12, 49-62.
14. Smith, PC & Goddard, M 2002, 'Performance management and operational research: a marriage made in heaven?', Journal of the Operational Research Society, 53, 247-255.